

“INDIVIDUALIZED SPEECH STYLE” IN SPEECH TEACHING

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Abstract. Individual speech style is a conceptually important concept, moral, moralizing the entire process of rhetorical training of a future teacher. The individual style of speech is of particular importance for the teacher, since, firstly, the teacher's speech is a sample of the students' speech, and secondly, teaching the native language and literature requires thoughtfulness and awareness. The forms include familiarizing students with the linguistic culture of society, developing a caring attitude towards language, and consciously mastering language as a means of communication.

Key words: speech, education, pedagogy, rhetoric, speech style, teachers, individual speech, eloquence, communication.

NOTIQLIK TA'LIMOTIDA “INDIVIDUAL NUTQ USLUBI”

Annotatsiya. O'qituvchi uchun individual nutq uslubi alohida ahamiyatga ega, birinchidan, o'qituvchining nutqi o'quvchilar uchun nutq namunasi bo'lsa, ikkinchidan, ona tili va adabiyotini o'rgatish o'ychan va onglilikni talab qiladi. O'quvchilarni jamiyatning til madaniyati bilan tanishtirish, ularda tilga nisbatan ehtiyotkorona munosabatni shakllantirish, tilni muloqot vositasi sifatida ongli ravishda o'zlashtirish shakllaridir.

Kalit so'zlar: nutq, ta'lim, pedagogik, ritorika, nutq uslubi, o'qituvchilar, individual nutq, notiqlik, muloqot.

«ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНЫЙ СТИЛЬ РЕЧИ» В ОБУЧЕНИИ РЕЧИ

Аннотация. Индивидуальный стиль речи – концептуально важное понятие, нравственное, морализирующее весь процесс риторической подготовки будущего учителя.

Индивидуальный стиль речи имеет для учителя особое значение, поскольку, во-первых, речь учителя является образцом речи учащихся, а во-вторых, обучение родному языку и литературе требует вдумчивости и осознанности. Формами являются ознакомление учащихся с языковой культурой общества, формирование у них бережного отношения к языку, сознательное овладение языком как средством общения.

Ключевые слова: речь, образование, педагогика, риторика, стиль речи, педагоги, индивидуальная речь, красноречие, общение.

It is determined by the need to ensure the effectiveness of teaching activities in the pedagogical educational system, to improve speech skills, to form oneself as an inquisitive person, to educate a creative personality capable of nurturing creative individuality in students. Of particular importance in the context of solving the problem of teaching pedagogical skills is the development of an individual style of professional speech as an indicator of communication skills and the highest level of creative approach to their profession. The individual style of speech has always attracted the attention of speakers, teachers and Methodists as an integral feature of a skillful orator, talented speaker, teacher.

Pedagogical rhetoric is one of the professionally oriented rhetoric, the main task of which is to teach effective pedagogical communication, develop professional speech skills, become a communicative personality of the professional.

Individual speech style is a conceptually important concept that makes the entire process of rhetorical training of the future teacher meaningful. For the teacher, the style of individual speech is of particular importance, firstly, when the teacher's speech is a speech pattern for students, and secondly, teaching his native language and literature requires thoughtfulness and awareness. Familiarization of students with the language culture of society, the formation of a careful attitude towards language in them, the conscious assimilation of language as a means of communication are forms.

This conceptual approach requires more specific theoretical and practical development, both in the field of self-clarification of the concept and in the field of methodological methods for the development of an individual style of professional speech. At its center stands the uniqueness of the teacher, who reveals and refines his creative rhetorical abilities in the field of professional communication.

Obviously, the teacher should not only have communicative and speech skills at a high professional level, but also be distinguished by his creative attitude to solving the educational tasks facing him, his individual approach to finding optimal ways to solve these problems.

The experience of an individual creative approach to achieving methodological goals is also important as a proven method in personal experience to teach students the criteria for speech behavior and develop their individual rhetorical abilities. At its center stands the uniqueness of the teacher, who reveals and refines his creative rhetorical abilities in the field of professional communication. Obviously, the teacher should not only have communicative and speech skills at a high professional level, but also be distinguished by his creative attitude to solving the educational tasks facing him, his individual approach to finding optimal ways to solve these problems.

The appeal to the study of the genre of interpretive speech in terms of the manifestation of an individual style is due to its great professional importance in the speech practice of the teacher.

Knowing the possible ways to show an individual style in this genre with stable and effective communicative practice at the initial level of mastering will ensure a qualitative transfer of the communicative skills of the future teacher in the educational process to another sphere.

Genres of pedagogical speech. The experience of an individual creative approach to achieving methodological goals is also important as a proven method in personal experience to teach students the norms of speech behavior and develop their individual rhetorical abilities.

O.S. Explaining what style is, akhmonova noted: "as a person uses speech, he does not mean simply saying what he is, but saying what is said in a way that leaves the establishment, a certain influence, an indication. Such types of effects achieved by selecting specific words and constructing sentences are called methodological effects. The science of such means of influence is methodological" [2].

A special place is occupied by the "style" as a way of expressing thought, the "individual style" as an individual way of speech, the ways of developing and improving the individual style in the rhetorical and methodological work of the past.

"The style should not be too low, too high, but it should match the theme of speech" [1].

The study of the individual style of speech as a reflection of the communicative personality of the speaker is relevant and promising. Science analyzes the linguistic means of manifestation of the individual style of speech in different functional styles of speech and types of genres

In conclusion, according to many scientists, the manifestation of an individual style in the genres of scientific style of speech is completely natural and logical. In popular science texts (M.N.Kozhina, R.K. Tereshkina, E.S.Troyanskaya, M.P.Works by Senkevich et al.) there is a wider range of possibilities for expressing author individuality. It is clearly manifested in the choice of means of enhancing the individual style of speech in the genre of explanatory speech, which combines the features of Educational, Scientific and popular styles, for which it is natural to use tools with an individual stylistic color. The expressiveness of speech consists in rhetorical figures, intonation.

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